

Lit.: Key, Harold H., Morphology of Cayuvava, 1967
Hayes...

I. Segmental Properties

Phonotactic patterns

- all C and V in any respective C or V position (with limitation of the CC cluster of the CCV syllable)
- semiV in any C or V position
- occurrence of C-value of semiV only in small list of words

Phonological processes

C-fluctuations:

- /p/ and /t/ → /b/ and /d/ adjacent to syllables with initial voiced C
e.g. /papirikoha/ 'you believe' vs. /pabikçh/ ~ /babikçha/ 'they believe'
- morpheme-initial /t/ → /r/ when preceded by the morpheme /ki/
/ki/ subordinator + /tiporihi/ 'he lives, endures' → /kiriporihi/ 'while he lives, endures'
- /r/ of the morpheme /risɬç/ → /d/ when preceded by N-stem to build compounds
/ka'napæpæ/ 'bread' + /risɬç/ 'new' + /hiki/ 'corn' → /kana'pæpæ di'sɬçhiki/
'green corn tamale'
- /h/ → /sɬ/ adjacent to high front V /i/ (/e/)
/pabiha/ ~ /pabisɬa/ 'it hurts'

Nasalization:

- /d/ → /n/ (only) in the prominent /ada/ morpheme (kind of reflexive-passive action)
/ada/ + /bõhõ/ 'suffer' → /anabõhõ/ 'he is caused to suffer'
- nasalization of certain C and V adjacent to syllables with any nasalized segment
/arihitãhãæ/ ~ /arihiÚtãhãæ/

V-loss and fluctuation:

- V ranked in strength, i.e. V occurring adjacent to another V, then the more fronted one will be eliminated e.g. /ki/ + /ucɬãrãhi/ 'he is coming' → /kucɬãrãhi/ 'when he is already coming', /apa/ 'your' + /uaba/ 'body' → /apuaba/ 'your body'
- one isolated assimilation: /e/ + /u/ → /o/ + /o/
/ye/ 'not' + /huhuneriki/ 'I see them' → /yohohuneriki/ 'I not see them'

- /ki/ 'while' + negative indicator /ye/: /y/ → /cɰ/ → no reduction of the V /i/, /ɔ/ or /æ/ in clusters have been encountered
- Vowel harmony prominent role in Cayuvava texts, but for the most part it is due to a function of reduplication

Default syllable template

- Syllable patterns: V or VC; CCV under specific stress circumstances
- no vowel length distinction → /VV/ represents a disyllabic sequence

Super heavy syllables or trimoraics?

- Cayuvava has only light syllables

II. Prosodic Properties

Stress

- initial in disyllables, otherwise antepenultimate (tri-syllabic stress-group patterns; beginning with final syllable every third syllable is stressed) → rightmost stress strongest
- Fixed system, interrupted by morphemes with own relation to strong stress; irregular penultimate and final stress in certain morphological contexts
- Trochee
- extension of the 3 syllable type of structure with antepenult stress
- constructions of 3n+2 syllables (i.e. 5, 8, or 11 syllables): the first two syllables remain stress less → double upbeat is anomalous ↗ Hayes p. 309 - 314 (different claims: vowel deletion, weak stress on first syllable)
- clitics: when suffixed to a verb stem the usual stress is affected: → stress occurs on the final syllable of the stem adjacent to the newly affixed enclitic and the tri-syllabic anticipatory stress pattern must be adjusted to accommodate the locative clitic
- non-root or semi-root morphemes as particles can occur as separate words with independent stress pattern

Tone system

- none

III. Morpho-Syntax

Degree and types of fusion

- concatenative, phonological bound, segmentable morphemes
- different simple root morphemes (primary roots) can be composed by affixation of secondary root morphemes
- different inflection incorporating constructions
- basic root stem at center of construction +/- prefixes and/or suffixes

- word-class indicators and classes of affixes satellitic to morphemes functioning in syntactic position
- combinations of non-roots and affix morphemes
- derivation which incorporates inflection without roots → constructions composed of affix morphemes, verbalized by the /a/ verbalizer morpheme
- verbal derivation with pronouns → function syntactically as AUX or pronouns
- no non-adjacent allomorphy

Infixation, circumfixation, simulfixation

- none

Reduplication patterns

- Reduplication → inflectional process in direct reference to base-stem
- 9 kinds of reduplication:
 - R 1 (partial): /rV/, i.e. /r/ + reduplication of final V of the base verb root, e.g. /Be/ → /Bere/ 'run'
 - R 2 (partial/total): R whole root or initial syllable, e.g. /Bere/ 'run' → /BeBere/ process of running
 - R 3 (partial): = R 2 but second syllable of the root, e.g. /t'idi/ → /t'idi'di/ 'carrying on shoulder'
 - R 4: clusters of double vowels within a root, not of two syllables → internal R, not a functioning process, no underlying form, e.g. */rucɬa/ → i.e. this formation a closed derivational process, not a functioning or productive, e.g. /ruucɬa/ 'to leave, abandon'
 - R 5 (total): complete R of root of morpheme, e.g. /a'dɕadɕ/ 'wring out in cloth'
 - R 6: secondary R of an almost redupl. root !no evidence!
 - R 7 (partial): secondary R of the final syllable /rV/ (maybe almost R 1), e.g. /cærae/ → /cæraerae/ 'mock, imitate'
 - R 8: secondary R: composition of R 2 + R 1, e.g. /cɕcɕjɕrɕ/ state of being found, finding
 - R 9: complex phonemic shapes of certain R-patterns, R-combinations of R1 + R5 + R1/R3, e.g. /je/ 'move' + R1 → /jere/ 'cause to move' + R 5 → /jerejere/ 'moving right along' + R1 → /jere'jerere/ 'cause to move along, to hurry one along'

Clitics and particles.

- particles have no affixation but may be derived from simple roots or compounds of root in constructions

Proclitics:

- function more independently than the class of affix morphemes (i.e. aren't satellitic to one class of words, but may occur with either nouns or verbs)

- /me/ ~ /mei/ ~ /m/ (plural of noun words/constructions) → has inflectional characteristics functioning on a phrase level (e.g. /mei'araï/ 'nights')
- /ki/ ~ /k/ ~ /i/ 'the, a; while, when' (subordinator or indicator of a subordinated element; e.g. /k/ + /apapa/ 'my father' → /'kapapa/ 'my father', functioning as subject)
- /ka/ ~ /k/ 'that which, what' (e.g. /kahi'jorue/ 'that which, what I find')
- /ji/ ~ /j/ 'with, by' (e.g. /japarua/ 'in, with your hand') → occurs with other proclitic constructions: /ji'meiBe'deñika/ 'with house-owners'

Clitics and enclitics:

- often suffixed to verb stems
- also preceding noun stems when the agentive /ji/ occurs immediately before a noun
- in noun constructions: no distinctive stress pattern has been recognized
- but in verb constructions: stress is affected (↗ above)
- true shape: verb stem: /'Vtui/ 'up, upward' (V = final vowel of the verb stem)
noun stem: /tu/ + /ji/ + noun stem

Particles:

- roots or compounds which occur as separate words → more freedom of occurrence and more independence from the stress pattern (separate word stress and can occur alone)
- simple roots, e.g. /haaa/ 'yes' (from a man), /hããã/ 'yes' (from a woman), /ñõhõ/ 'now', /norol/ 'almost' ...
- complex stems, e.g. /yaBe/ 'very' + /iiñe/ 'again, and' → /yaBe'iiñe/ 'also, a lot'
- some occur in constructions with others, e.g. /ji/ and also with personal pronoun suffixes (e.g. /ji/ + /iki/ → /jiiki/ 'with them') → no suffix to a particle (impossible), but a construction of two morphemes just as particles occur with all classes of morphemes to build new, separate words that function in particle position
- one complex form /yaore/ 'soon, right away' also occurs with complete reduplication of the second root → /yao'reore/ 'right now, instantly'

IV. Other Questions

- no reduction
- in disyllables, foot constructions creates degenerate feet, which survive because Word Layer Construction places them in strong position

Word-word combinations (e.g. compounds, incorporation, complex predicates).

- in verb constructions there are up to 6 prefixes and 5 suffixes
- nouns: combinations of roots with certain limitations:
 - no C alone may be a noun root
 - no Cs adjacent within any root (except in rare borrowed words)

→ not necessarily compounds, but simple stems with non-isolating morphemic content (compare engl. *ceive* of *receive* or *cran* of *cranberry*)

Compound stems (construction of two or more roots)

- noun root (head item as being possessed) + noun root (modifier as being possessor), e.g. /he'bækafe/ 'coffee hull' (*kafe* borrowed from Spanish)
- fusion of root morphemes → sometimes with loss of distinct morpheme boundaries (e.g. /ridore/ 'it burns' + /maka/ 'sun' → /rido'remaka/ 'a year')
→ and compounds without clearly marked morphemic boundaries (e.g. /ñera'barike/ 'river')
- verb-stem + noun-stem (the latter functioning as object of the preceding verb-stem)
e.g. /Bede/ 'have' + /ñika/ 'house' → / Be'deñika/ 'house-owner'
- noun stems (as constructions of modifying root, e.g. reduplication) + noun root
- noun stems as constructions of modifier root prefixed to noun or verb stem

Complex stems (formed by combinations of one root with one or more non-roots or semi-roots)

- no bipartite stems

Periphrastic morphology:

- class of pronouns function syntactically as Aux or pronouns
- no pre- or postpositions